

Reaction of β -aminocrotonitrile with acid chlorides : a study on regiopreference[†]

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Chemistry of β -aminocrotonitrile is well documented in the literature. However, systematic study on its acylation reaction with acid chlorides and its immense potential in synthesis has not yet been reported as review articles. This short review describes reaction and regiopreference of β -aminocrotonitrile when reacted with acid chlorides in presence of an organic base.

1. Introduction

Ever since the pioneering work of Stork¹ on the reactivity and synthetic applications of enamines, the growth of literature in this area has been exponential². However, not much information is available in the literature on the acylation reaction on primary enaminoitriles and the area remains largely unexplored. As early as 1922 Benary and coworkers³ reacted β -aminocrotonitrile **1** with a few carboxylic acid chlorides and reported isolation of C-acylated products which were converted to pyrazoles. A mixture of C- and N-acylated products were also obtained occasionally. A Japanese group⁴ reported exclusive formation of N-acetates on reacting **1** with acetic anhydride.

Carbonyl compounds and ketones in particular have been used generally as donors only following their preactivation by conversion into a more reactive species such as enols or enamine equivalent⁵. 1,3-Diketones are well-known precursors for synthesis of 1,2-azoles⁶. However, success of this simple and high yielding methodology is confined to the use of symmetrical diketones only as isomeric products result from unsymmetrical 1,3-diketones. This inherent drawback can be easily removed if masked 1,3-diketones are used which would ensure regioselectivity during synthesis of various heterocycles. α -Cyanoenaminones derived from C-acylation of enaminoitriles constitute such an important class of compounds⁷. However, the success of this approach largely depends on the preference for site selection during acylation reaction of enaminoitrile.

Although chemistry of β -enaminoitriles has been reviewed²ⁱ but any comprehensive study on their reaction with acid chlorides is yet to be reported. This short review describes the properties and reaction of β -aminocrotonitrile **1** with acid chlorides, aliphatic as well as aromatic including heteroaromatic in the presence of an added organic base and application of the derived α -cyanoenaminones in synthesis.

2. A brief account on the chemistry of β -aminocrotonitrile

Enamines are a three atom π -system, which are nitrogen analogues of enols^{2b}. In principle, an enamine can react with an electrophile either on nitrogen or on carbon as shown by the following resonance forms (**2** \leftrightarrow **3**).

An additional reacting site can also be developed in an enamine with extended conjugation (**4-6**). However, such a situation can only be materialized if the nitrogen in **4** is tertiary in nature, since primary and secondary vinylamines predominate in their imine form⁸.

Exceptions are the primary enamines with electron withdrawing group (EWG) e.g. enamino ketone, ester and ni-

[†]Dedicated to Professor S. M. Mukherji

Table 1

 IR (ν_{\max} in cm^{-1}): 3450, 3350, 1645, 2180, 1600

UV		Z-isomer λ_{\max} (MeCN) = 254 nm, $\epsilon = 11.77 \times 10^4$		E-isomer λ_{\max} (MeCN) = 255 nm, $\epsilon = 1.54 \times 10^4$	
$^1\text{H NMR}$ (δ ppm)	Solvent	$>=\text{C}^{\text{H}}$	$>=\text{CCH}_3$	-NH	J (Hz)
1b					
Saturated solution	Benzene	3.64	1.50	Not observed	H/CH ₃ (0)
1b + 1a					
Dilute solution	Benzene	3.63	1.03	Not observed	H/CH ₃ (0.8)
1a (Z)	CDCl ₃	3.89	1.92	-	H/CH ₃ (0.75 \pm 2)
1b (E)	CDCl ₃	4.10	2.09	4.68	-

aminocrotonitrile. A mixture of *E*- and *Z*-isomers, which are readily distinguishable by $^1\text{H NMR}$ is formed during preparation of this compound by usual methods of preparation as only the *Z*-isomer **1a** has allylic coupling constant of 0.8 Hz for the methyl group. In addition, the *Z*-isomer absorbs in UV spectroscopy at shorter wavelength and usually gives a more intense absorption band than does the *E*-isomer¹⁹. The position of the photoequilibrium, as established by UV absorption data is at (75%) *Z*-form and (25%) *E*-form.

Kuthan²⁰ has made HMO study with some enamionitriles (Fig. **D**₁-**D**₄). The conjugation in the system $\text{H}_2\text{N}-\text{C}=\text{C}-\text{CN}$, may significantly influence the stability and other physical as well as chemical properties of this type of compounds. Simple LCAO-HMO principle has been applied to interpret their properties and an attempt has been made to correlate π -electron distribution and chemical reactivity of such systems.

From the comparison of the diagram of vinyl amine **D**₁ with that of cyano derivative **D**₂, it follows that introduction of a terminal cyano group somewhat increases participation of non-bonding orbital of nitrogen atom in π -electron system i.e. increases the π -bond order of $-\text{C}-\text{NH}_2$ bond. On the other hand, it follows from the molecular diagram of enamionitriles **D**₂-**D**₄ that introduction of methyl or phenyl groups to position C-3 exerts quite opposite effect, however, at the same time it increases the conjugation with cyano group (decrease of π -bond orders of the $\text{C}-\text{NH}_2$ and $\text{C}=\text{C}$ bonds and increase of π -bond orders of $\text{C}-\text{CN}$ bonds).

Based on this hypothesis the author suggested that reaction of β -enamionitriles **8** with acyl halides and aldehydes should proceed to give compounds **9** and **10** respectively in agreement with the maximum values of superdelocalisation S_n in position C-2.

Molecular diagram of some enamionitriles

It is also very important to note that resonance hybrid of enamine structure imparts certain nucleophilic character to some atoms while other atoms are electrophilic¹⁰, since the Michael addition features so prominently²¹ (Scheme 1).

4. Preparation of β -aminocrotonitrile

The dimerization of acetonitrile in presence of sodium

Scheme 1

in organic solvents is the most common approach for the synthesis of β -aminocrotononitrile. The reaction proceeds via a free radical mechanism¹⁰ (Scheme 2).

Scheme 2

β -Aminocrotononitrile **1** prepared by the method of Adkins and Whitman²² was obtained as a mixture of *Z*- and *E*-isomers (**1a** and **1b**). Bullock *et al.*^{18a} developed a procedure whereby it was possible to separate the two isomers under highly controlled conditions. On the basis of spectral evidences, the higher melting (78–80°) isomer has been designated as the *Z*-isomer **1a** while the lower melting (44–46°) one represents the *E*-isomer **1b**. Very recently, Gerhard and coworkers²³ reported a modified method originally developed by Adkins and Whitman for the preparation of **1** in excellent yield. The modification employs reaction of acetonitrile with sodium in gasoline under nitrogen at 105–110°/3–5 bar followed by controlled hydrolysis with water.

5. Reaction of β -aminocrotononitrile with acid chlorides in presence of sodium in refluxing benzene

Mahalanabis *et al.*²⁴ initially attempted acylation of **1** with benzoyl chloride in the presence of sodium in refluxing benzene. Unfortunately this reaction turned out to be extremely complex and devoid of any practical value (Scheme 3).

Scheme 3

Isolation of *N*-benzoylisopropylamine **11** as the major product clearly indicates that during the course of the reaction reductive cleavage of the cyano group occurred. Elimination of benzylic cyano group on Birch reduction²⁵ and reductive decyanation of α -cyanocarbanions in the presence of alkali metals in HMPT have been reported²⁶. Adkins and Whitman²² isolated isopropylamine as one of the products of hydrogenation with aliphatic enaminonitrile. This novel reductive decyanation of **1**, to the best of our knowledge appears to be the first example reported in literature. A tentative mechanism involving radical addition has been proposed²⁴. That sodium dust is actually responsible for such unusual reductive decyanation of **1** comes from the observation that when benzoylation was carried out in presence of sodium hydride in benzene, *C,N*-dibenzoylated β -aminocrotononitrile **16** was obtained as the sole product from the reaction mixture. In order to explore the generality of this reaction Mahalanabis and coworkers studied benzoylation of different β -aryl- β -enaminonitriles **19** in presence of sodium in refluxing benzene. A complex mixture of products viz. β -aryl- β -amino- α -benzoylacrylonitrile **20**, pyrimidine **21**, dihydropyridine **22**, β -ketonitriles **23**, **24**, **25** and benzamide **15** were obtained²⁴ (Table 2).

The formation of pyrimidine derivatives **21** resulted due to the intervention of a radical process. It was further observed that this type of reductive decyanation during acylation is limited only to β -aminocrotononitrile **1** as enaminonitrile **18** failed to undergo reductive decyanation under the same experimental conditions, the major product isolated from the reaction mixture being the corresponding *C*-benzoylated

Table 2

19	21	20
a : Ar = Ph	21a	20a
b : Ar = <i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	21b	20b
c : Ar = <i>p</i> -MeOC ₆ H ₄	21c	20c
The other products are :		
a : Ar = Ph		
	22	15
b : Ar = <i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄		
	23	24
c : Ar = <i>p</i> -MeOC ₆ H ₄		
	25	16

derivative **17** with a trace quantity of benzamide **15**.

6.1. Reaction of β -aminocrotonitrile with saturated acid chlorides in the presence of an added organic base :

As early as 1922 Benary *et al.*³ could recognise the importance of β -aminocrotonitrile and studied the reaction of monochloroacetyl chloride and phenoxyacetyl chloride with β -aminocrotonitrile in the presence of pyridine in absolute ether. In both cases corresponding C-acylated products were obtained as proved by their conversion to pyrazoles. Since this study was done in isolation and was limited in scope, Mahalanabis *et al.*²⁷ reinvestigated the reaction of β -aminocrotonitrile with a large number of acid chlorides, both aliphatic and aromatic including heteroaromatic. The presence of an added organic base is essential for the success of the reactions. In absence of base, liberated hydrochloric acid catalyzed the spontaneous polymerization of the enamionitrile itself²⁸. The results of this study is summarized in Table 3.

Assignment of structures for all these compounds was based on elemental and extensive spectral analyses and are firmly secured. The most notable feature in the ¹H NMR spectra is the signals for the -NH protons which appear at two regions, namely, δ 6.0–7.0 and δ 10.2–11.2 ppm, respectively. Incidentally, Hayashi *et al.*²⁹ found that all the ¹H NMR spectra of the α -cyano- β -alkyl- β -aminoacrylic esters showed two broadened signals with equal intensity in the region δ 5.56–6.00 and δ 9.20–10.02 ppm, respectively. The signal appearing in the lower field is evidently due to the hydrogen bonded -NH proton. It was also noted

Table 3. Acylation of 1 with saturated acid chlorides

RCOCl	Compd.	Acylation	Yield (%)
R = CH ₃	26a	C	70
R = CH ₂ Cl	26b	C	72
R = CHCl ₂	26c	C	71
R = CCl ₃	26d	C	70
R = CH ₂ CH ₃	26e	C	77
R = CH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₃	26f	C	74
R = CH(CH ₃) ₂	27g	N	78
R = C(CH ₃) ₃	27h	N	72
R = Ph	26i, 27i	C, N	80
R = CH ₂ Ph	26j, 27j	C, N	78
R = CH ₂ CH ₂ Ph	26k	C	75
R = CH ₂ -O-C ₆ H ₃ Cl ₂ (2,4)	26l	C	85
R = 2-Furyl	26m	C	71
R = 2-Thienyl	26n, 27n	C, N	69
R = <i>o</i> -MeOC ₆ H ₄	26o, 27o	C, N	70
R = <i>m</i> -MeOC ₆ H ₄	27p	N	74
R = <i>p</i> -MeOC ₆ H ₄	27q	N	76
R = <i>o</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	26r, 27r	C, N	71
R = <i>m</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	26s, 27s	C, N	73
R = <i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	26t	C	69
R = <i>o</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	27u	N	71
R = <i>m</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	27v	N	70
R = <i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	26w, 27w	C, N	74

that in all cases of C-acylation, only *Z*-isomer was obtained and this may be attributed to the formation, at least in solution, of chelated species **26**.

¹H NMR spectra of N-acylated enamionitriles **27**, on the other hand, showed complete absence of any signals around δ 10.2–11.16 ppm, a unique characteristic associated with chelated -NH proton of C-acylated compounds. Here, the -NH proton signal appears as a broad singlet in the region δ 7.26–7.80 ppm and the olefinic proton appears at δ 6.43–6.66 ppm. Thus, the presence of C- and N-acylated products in the reaction mixtures can be easily ascertained by careful examination of ¹H NMR spectra of the crude products. In addition, carbonyl signal of the C-acylated product appears around δ 200 ppm whereas amide carbonyl signal of the N-acylated product appears around δ 180 ppm in ¹³C NMR spectra.

This study, for the first time, demonstrated that preference for site selection in acylation reaction of β -aminocrotonitrile **1** can be controlled, to a large extent, by choice of acid chlorides. Whereas with aliphatic acid chlorides the terminal selection of the enamionitrile was found to be highly selective, such pronounced selectivity

Scheme 4

was not observed with aromatic and heteroaromatic acid chlorides in all cases. It is quite apparent from this study that substituents (EDG/EWG) as well as their position of attachment in the aromatic ring do exert a strong influence in site selection during acylation of **1**.

6.2. Reaction of β -aminocrotononitrile with α,β -unsaturated acid chlorides :

Mahalanabis *et al.*³⁰ have observed that when β -aminocrotononitrile **1** was reacted with α,β -unsaturated acid chlorides **28** in the presence of triethylamine as an added organic base, a series of 3,4-dihydro-2-(1H)-pyridones **29** were obtained (Scheme 5).

Scheme 5

N-Acylation followed by *in situ* intramolecular ring closure accounts for the formation of **29**. The structural assignment for **29** was deduced from elemental and spectroscopic

analysis. For example, ¹³C NMR spectrum of **29c** ($R_1 = p\text{-MeC}_6\text{H}_4$, $R_2 = R_3 = \text{H}$) shows singlet at δ 170.6 (C=O), 148.3 (C-6), 89.5 (C-5), 38.4 (C-4), and 37.5 (C-3) ppm. Additional support in favour of 3,4-dihydro-2-(1H)-pyridone structure accrued from the preparation of authentic samples of **29a**³¹, **29b**³¹ and **29l**³². It is quite interesting to note that whereas acylation in the presence of triethylamine afforded 3,4-dihydro-2-(1H)-pyridones **29** in all cases such regioselectivity was, however, not always observed when triethylamine was replaced by pyridine. Acylation of **1** with cinnamoyl chloride and *p*-nitrocinnamoyl chloride in presence of pyridine furnished a mixture of 3,4-dihydro-2-(1H)-pyridones **29a**, **29h**, and C-acylated products **30a**, **30h**, in equal proportions (Scheme 6). These results indicate the underlying importance of the added organic base as it appears to impart considerable influence in directing the site of acylation of enaminonitrile **1**.

Scheme 6

Interestingly, Benary³ reported isolation of a 1 : 1 mixture of C-acylated product **30a** and N-acylated product **31a** when **1** was reacted with cinnamoyl chloride in the presence of pyridine. Reinvestigation of Benary work by Mahalanabis *et al.*³³ revealed that Benary designated N-acylated product **31a** was in fact dihydropyridone **29a** formed via *in situ* [3,3] sigmatropic rearrangement of **31a**.

Since enamines are ambident nucleophiles the reaction can occur at the nitrogen or at the β -carbon atom. N-Acylenamine, if formed, has an alternative reaction path available viz. [3,3] sigmatropic rearrangement to give a ketene intermediate. Cyclization of the regenerated enamine system on to the ketene affords an enolate anion which is subsequently protonated to yield 3,4-dihydro-2-(1H)-pyridones **29**. This postulate finds adequate support from the work of Hickmott *et al.*³⁴.

Structural assignment for either **29a** or **32a** becomes somewhat perplexing as UV, IR and ¹H NMR spectral data for isomeric dihydropyridones are not conclusive³⁵. What-

ever way these compounds are formed they are vinylogous and their UV, IR and ^1H NMR data cannot be used with certainty for structural assignment purpose. Moreover, the high absorption maxima and extinction coefficients in the UV of the parent enamionitrile itself remaining intact in both **29a** and **32a**, a comparison of these data for structural elucidation as described in the literature³² should not be taken for granted.

In the ^1H NMR spectra both **29** and **32** are expected to exhibit similar proton signal patterns allowing only recognition of their gross structure. Analysis of ^1H NMR spectrum (500 MHz) of **29a** or **32a** coupled with NOE experiments showed a singlet at δ 2.24 ppm assigned to 6-methyl protons, a pair of double doublets centered at δ 2.78 ppm (J 5.7, 16.7 Hz) were assigned to 3- H_a , H_b protons. 4- H_c proton appeared at δ 3.89 ppm as double doublet (J 5.7, 7.7 Hz) and the aromatic protons appeared as multiplet centered at δ 7.35 ppm. A broad signal at δ 7.92 ppm was assigned to -NH proton. Based on these observations it can be concluded, with a fair degree of certainty, that compound **29a** or **32a** represents a dihydropyridone ring with H-C-H group at C-3 rather than N-acylated compound **31a** as claimed by Benary. In contrast, ^{13}C NMR spectrum of **29a** or **32a** should be highly informative. Thus, in **29a** the C-4 is expected to appear at δ 26–30 ppm whereas in compound **32a** the C-2 should appear at a much higher field³⁶ (50–55 ppm). Furthermore, the carbonyl carbon signal of **29a** and **32a** should also differ considerably³⁷. ^{13}C NMR spectrum (pyridine- d_5) analysis of **29a/32a** showed among other signals, a doublet at δ 40 ppm corresponding to C-4 of **29a** and a singlet appearing at δ 169.3 ppm was assigned to -NHCO- group of **29a**, thus establishing the fine structure of dihydropyridone unequivocally.

Acylation of **1** with cinnamoyl chloride in the presence of pyridine (Scheme 6) showed in the crude reaction mixture unmistakable presence of C-acylated product **30a** along with dihydropyridone **29a** as detected by ^1H NMR spectrum. This observation provided invaluable information with regard to the participating intermediate species responsible for formation of **29a/32a**. The presence of **30a** precluded its participation in the cyclization process leading to the formation of **32a**. It was further observed that **30a** failed to cyclise even at elevated temperature in refluxing diphenyl ether. In view of these observations it can be safely concluded that formation of **29a** must have resulted from *in situ* cyclization of N-acylenaminonitrile **31a** via sigmatropic rearrangement. Acylation reaction of **1** with α,β -unsaturated acid chlorides in presence of triethylamine shows exclusive preference without any exception for N-terminal.

6.2.1. Reaction of β -aminocrotonitrile with acid chlorides of 2,4-hexadienoic acid and phenyl propiolic acid:

While generality of enamine reactivity to produce cleanly the corresponding 3,4-dihydropyridin-2(1H)-one in the presence of triethylamine has been found to be well documented³⁰ with α,β -unsaturated acid chlorides, a complete reversal of regioselectivity was observed when **1** was reacted with acid chlorides obtained from 2,4-hexadienoic acid and phenyl propiolic acid³³. C-Acylated products were obtained in excellent yields (Scheme 7).

Scheme 7

7. α -Cyano- β -enaminones : application to synthesis

Easy access to α -cyano- β -enaminones by reacting β -aminocrotonitrile with suitable acid chlorides in presence of an added organic base has provided an extremely facile, and highly regiospecific synthesis of polysubstituted 1,2-azoles from a common intermediate. Thus, a short and expeditious regiospecific synthesis of pyrazoles with novel variants at C-5 which are otherwise difficult to prepare in good to excellent yield is recently reported from this laboratory³⁸. Mahalanabis *et al.*³⁹ have also completed synthesis of a large number of highly functionalised 5-isoxazolones and isoxazoles. Cyanoenaminones are also successfully converted to 5-substituted-4-cyanoisothiazoles⁴⁰.

7.1. 3,4-Dihydro-2(1H)-pyridone : Conversion to 2(1H)-pyridones, pyridines and 3,4-dihydro-2(1H)-thiopyridones :

3,4-Dihydro-2(1H)-pyridones were successfully converted to 2(1H)-pyridones³⁰, highly substituted 2-chloropyridine derivatives⁴¹, 3,4-dihydro-2(1H)-pyridinthiones and 2(1H)-pyridinthiones⁴².

Conclusion

Acylation reactions of β -aminocrotonitrile with different acid chlorides in presence of an added organic base exhibit a strong preference for terminal selection depending on the acid chloride used.

This study also provides a very simple and highly efficient high yielding methodology for the preparation of α -cyano- β -enaminones considered to be versatile synthons towards synthesis of various heterocycles and alkaloids⁴³.

The N-acylated enaminonitriles can also serve as useful intermediates. Photocyclisation of enamides is extensively used for synthesis of complex natural products⁴⁴.

Acylation of β -aminocrotonitrile with aliphatic acid chlorides in the presence of pyridine was found to be totally regiocontrolled. However, no such definite trend could be observed with aromatic and heteroaromatic acid chlorides during acylation of **1**.

α,β -Unsaturated acid chlorides appear to be more versatile when compared to α,β -unsaturated esters⁴⁵ and amides⁴⁶ used as Michael acceptors with enaminonitriles. In addition, these are limited to methyl acrylate and methacrylate only imposing serious limitations on introduction of substituents in the dihydropyridine ring.

Furthermore, β -aminocrotonitrile **1** is found to be better synthon than β -aminocrotonate in acylation reaction with acid chlorides as it provides only Z-isomer whereas, with enaminoester, a mixture of geometrical isomers (E,Z) of the corresponding C-acylated products are obtained in most of the cases studied so far⁴¹.

The work presented here suggests scope for more theoretical or semi theoretical work to understand clearly the implications of different factors that influence the preference for terminal selection. However, some empirical generalisation can be made from the results reported here.

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